

6 Appendix

6.1 Related Works

Recent advances in automated quantum circuit design are driven by two key challenges: circuit structure strongly influences trainability, expressivity, and hardware compatibility, and the search space over gate types, connectivity, and depth is combinatorial. Consequently, quantum circuit synthesis and quantum neural architecture search (QNAS) are increasingly formulated as optimization problems, often using evolutionary or neuroevolutionary algorithms that jointly explore discrete structures and continuous parameters.

One major direction focuses on constrained circuit synthesis. Sünkel et al. [56] propose a hybrid multi-objective evolutionary approach optimizing fidelity and circuit depth, achieving strong depth reductions with minimal fidelity loss. Unlike such work, which targets synthetic objectives, the present approach emphasizes dataset-driven tasks and backend-agnostic training across frameworks such as PennyLane and Qiskit. Similarly, Zhang and Zhao [65] apply evolutionary search to classification using measurement-based metrics, whereas this work additionally supports fidelity-based supervision when target mappings are available.

Neuroevolution-based methods such as QNEAT [14] co-evolve circuit topology and parameters, demonstrating effectiveness in RL settings. In contrast, the proposed framework employs a unified genome representation that supports both task-based losses and circuit-to-circuit or state fidelity objectives. Ding and Spector [10] further emphasize multi-objective optimization, balancing accuracy and circuit complexity, aligning with our use of structural metrics to discourage inefficient architectures.

In supervised learning, EQNAS [30], Li et al. [31], and Ma et al. [37] demonstrate evolutionary QNAS for classification tasks such as MNIST and CIFAR-10. However, these methods typically rely on measurement-space objectives and pre-defined templates. The present work extends this paradigm by enabling fidelity-based supervision when a target circuit is available, while also supporting standard dataset-driven losses through readout distributions.

Representation design is another key aspect. Lourens et al. [34] propose hierarchical encodings to improve scalability and genetic operations. Similarly, the genome representation here emphasizes modularity through gate specifications, register-aware wiring, and flexible input-output mappings, while supporting backend-independent execution and multiple training objectives. Ewen et al. [13] explore genetic programming with ZX-calculus transformations, highlighting semantics-aware mutation strategies compatible with this framework.

Hybrid quantum-classical architectures have also been explored. Liu et al. [32] and Rubio et al. [48] investigate evolutionary search in hybrid models. The present work instead focuses on a general-purpose circuit genome capable of supporting both fidelity-based and dataset-driven learning, while incorporating richer evaluation signals beyond accuracy.

Prior work in quantum reinforcement learning largely focuses on optimizing parameters of fixed circuit architectures. Chen *et.al.* [7] replace classical Q-networks with VQCs, while Jerbi et.al. [19] extend this to policy-gradient methods. Other studies highlight optimization strategies and training stability [26], or formulate circuit construction as an RL problem [1]. In contrast, the proposed work shifts focus from parameter tuning within fixed ansätze to evolving circuit structure itself, enabling discovery of transferable architectures across both supervised and RL tasks.

6.2 EXAQC’s Distributed Asynchronous Framework

The evolutionary search is parallelized using a master-worker paradigm implemented with MPI via `mpi4py` (Refer Figure 5). The master process (rank 0) is responsible for generating candidate genomes and maintaining the population, while worker processes asynchronously request genomes, evaluate them using the objective function, and return the evaluated genomes back to the master for insertion into the population. This design enables efficient task distribution, as workers operate independently without synchronization barriers, allowing heterogeneous evaluation times across genomes. The asynchronous communication pattern ensures high resource utilization and scalability, significantly reducing overall search time for computationally expensive quantum circuit evaluations. The primary advantages of this parallelism include near-linear speedup with additional workers, improved exploration of the search space through increased evaluation throughput, and the ability to scale to large populations and complex objective functions without introducing significant coordination overhead. In its current initial implementation, EXAQC utilizes a single steady state population, however the codebase has been designed to allow for plugging in varying population strategies so it can be easily extended to utilize island or multiobjective strategies in future work.

6.3 Mutation and Crossover Operators

Add Gate (Figure 6a) places a gate at a random depth $d \sim U(0, 1)$. To prevent adding gates which will not be used in useful computation, the gates in the network are traversed in order from 0 to d , to determine which qubits are affected by the inputs - these make the list of potential input qubits for the new gate. Similarly, the gates are traversed in reverse order from 1.0 to d , to determine which qubits are connected to the outputs by other gates - these make the list of potential output qubits for the new gate. If the list of input and output qubits are disjoint, only gates which have control (input) and target (output) qubits are allowed. The input qubits for the new gate are selected from the possible input qubits, and the output qubits for the new gate are selected from the possible output qubits. If the gate is parameterized, its parameters are initialized randomly $\sim U(-\pi, \pi)$. The parent circuit genome will be copied as the new child (inheriting parental circuit parameters), and the gate will be added to the child genome at depth d with a newly assigned innovation number.

Enable/Disable Gate (Figure 6b) first copies the parent as a child genome, then randomly selects from the child either an enabled gate to be disabled (for *disable gate*), or a disabled gate to be enabled (for *enable gate*). If *enable gate* is selected and there are no disabled gates, or *disable gate* is selected and there are no enabled gates, this mutation will return False so another mutation or crossover attempt can be made to generate a modified child.

Reorder Gate (Figure 6c) first copies the parent as a child genome, then randomly selects a gate within the child genome. It disables that gate, creates a copy of it (with a new innovation number), and assigns it a new depth $d \sim U(0, 1)$, a new innovation number, and adds it to the child genome.

Swap Qubits (Figure 6d) first copies the parent as a child genome, then randomly selects a gate within the child genome. It disables that gate, creates a copy of it (with a new innovation number), and then selects a qubit parameter at random with the gate and assigns it to a different qubit. If the qubit was an input qubit, the new qubit is randomly selected from all possible input qubits at that depth, if it was an output qubit, the new qubit is randomly selected from all possible output qubits at that depth. Otherwise (if it was both an input and output) it is randomly selected from all possible input and output qubits. Additionally, to prevent the new gate from having the same depth as the gate it was copied from, it is assigned a new depth $d \sim U(d_{prev}, d_{next})$, where d_{prev} is the depth of

Fig. 5: Master-Worker Architecture in Evolving Genome Circuits and Tracking the Best Genomes (*sim* is short for *simulation*)

the previous gate in the (sorted) gate list, or 0 if there was not a gate before it, and d_{max} is the depth of the next gate in the gate list, or 1.0 if there was not a gate after it. This new gate is assigned a new innovation number and added to the child genome.

N-Ary Crossover (Figure 7) expands binary crossover to allow any number of parents. Parents are divided into the best fit parent, and all other parents. If a gate exists in the best fit parent and any other parent, it is added to the child genome. If a gate is only in the best fit parent, it is added at the *best_keep_rate* (0.75 for this work). If a gate exists in any other gate, but not the best fit parent, it is added to the child genome at the *other_keep_rate* (0.25 for this work). For parameterized gates in multiple parents, a randomized simplex approach is used [22, 59], where the randomized line search is performed between weight in the best parent, p_{best} and the average of the weights in the other parents p_{avg} ,

Fig. 6: Structural mutation operators used in hybrid evolutionary quantum circuit optimization. Highlighted gates indicate newly added or modified structures. Figures first presented in Kar et al. [20].

Selection rules: If innovation i appears in the primary parent and in at least one other parent (yellow), it always transfers to the child. If i appears only in the primary parent (blue), it transfers with probability p_p . If i appears only in the other parents (orange), it transfers with probability p_o .

Parameter recombination (shared, parameterized gates): $r \leftarrow U(0, 1)(c_2 - c_1) + c_1$, $\bar{\theta}_{\text{others}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{O}_i|} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{O}_i} \theta_k$, $\theta_{\text{child}} = \theta_o + r(\bar{\theta}_p - \theta_o)$.

Other-only parameter averaging (when multiple others): For a selected other-only innovation with parameters, set $\beta_{\text{avg}} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j$.

Fig. 7: N-ary crossover operator (from Kar et al. [20]).

where $l_1 = -1.0$ and $l_2 = 0.5$ are used as hyperparameters:

$$\begin{aligned}
 r &= (\text{rand}(0, 1) * l_1) - l_2 \\
 p_{\text{new}} &= p_{\text{other}} + r * (p_{\text{best}} - p_{\text{other}})
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Gates which only come from one parent utilize the same weights. This follows EXAMM/EXA-GP’s Lamarckian weight inheritance strategy [36]. *Binary crossover* is n-ary crossover where $n = 2$.

Exponential Crossover Exponential crossover (Figure 8) was also implemented as a way to recombine parents in a way that could potentially capture different useful gates from each parent. This creates a new child genome, and computes a random crossover depth $d_{\text{crossover}} \sim U(0, 1)$. All gates from the first parent with depth $d < d_{\text{crossover}}$ are copied into the child genome, and all gates from the second parent with depth $d \geq d_{\text{crossover}}$ are copied from the second parent into the child genome.

Rule: Sample $d_c \sim U(0,1)$. Copy all gates from Parent 1 with depth $< d_c$, and all gates from Parent 2 with depth $\geq d_c$, into the child.

Fig. 8: Exponential crossover operator (from Kar et al. [20]).

6.4 Available Qiskit Gates

Gate	Method	Qubits	Parameters
Toffoli	cxx	control_qubit1, control_qubit2, target_qubit	
Symmetric	ccz	control_qubit1, control_qubit2, target_qubit	
Controlled Hadamard	ch	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Controlled Phase	cp	control_qubit, target_qubit	theta
Controlled RX	crx	control_qubit, target_qubit	theta
Controlled RY	cry	control_qubit, target_qubit	theta
Controlled RZ	crz	control_qubit, target_qubit	theta
Controlled S	cs	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Controlled S [†]	csdg	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Controlled SWAP (Fredkin)	cswap	control_qubit, target_qubit1, target_qubit2	
Controlled sqrt X	csx	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Controlled U	cu	control_qubit, target_qubit	theta, phi, lam, gamma
Controlled X	cx	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Controlled Y	cy	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Controlled Z	cz	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Double CNOT	dcx	qubit1, qubit2	
Echoed Cross-Resonance	ecr	qubit1, qubit2	
Hadamard	h	qubit	
Identity	id	qubit	
iSWAP	iswap	qubit1, qubit2	
Phase	p	qubit	theta
R	r	qubit	theta, phi
Simplified 3-Controlled Toffoli	rcccx	control_qubit1, control_qubit2, control_qubit3, target_qubit	
Simplified Toffoli (Margolus)	rccx	control_qubit1, control_qubit2, target_qubit	
RV	rv	qubit	vx, vy, vz
RX	rx	qubit	theta
RXX	rxx	qubit1, qubit2	theta
RY	ry	qubit	theta
RYY	ryy	qubit1, qubit2	theta
RZ	rz	qubit	phi
RZX	rxz	qubit1, qubit2	theta
RZZ	rzz	qubit1, qubit2	theta
S	s	qubit	
S-adjoint	sdg	qubit	
SWAP	swap	qubit1, qubit2	
sqrt X	sx	qubit	
inverse sqrt X	sxdg	qubit	
T	t	qubit	
T-adjoint	tdg	qubit	
U	u	qubit	theta, phi, lam
X	x	qubit	
Y	y	qubit	
Z	z	qubit	

Table 5: Available Qiskit gates, their qubits and parameters (if parameterized).

6.5 Available PennyLane Gates

Gate	Method	Qubits	Parameters
Toffoli	ccx	control_qubit1, control_qubit2, target_qubit	
CCZ	ccz	control_qubit1, control_qubit2, target_qubit	
Controlled Hadamard	ch	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Controlled Phase	cp	control_qubit, target_qubit	phi
Controlled RX	crx	control_qubit, target_qubit	phi
Controlled RY	cry	control_qubit, target_qubit	phi
Controlled RZ	crz	control_qubit, target_qubit	phi
Controlled SWAP (Fredkin)	cswap	control_qubit, target_qubit1, target_qubit2	
Controlled X	cx	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Controlled Y	cy	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Controlled Z	cz	control_qubit, target_qubit	
Hadamard	h	qubit	
Identity	id	qubit	
iSWAP	iswap	qubit1, qubit2	
Phase	p	qubit	phi
RX	rx	qubit	phi
RY	ry	qubit	phi
RZ	rz	qubit	phi
RZZ	rzz	qubit1, qubit2	theta
S	s	qubit	
SWAP	swap	qubit1, qubit2	
T	t	qubit	
U	u	qubit	theta, phi, delta
X	x	qubit	
Y	y	qubit	
Z	z	qubit	

Table 6: Available PennyLane gates, their qubits and parameters (if parameterized).

6.6 Best Found Classification Circuits

Fig. 9: Best found circuit for the iris benchmark.

Fig. 10: Best found circuit for the seeds benchmark.

6.7 Best Found Reinforcement Learning Circuits

(a) Best found circuit for CartPole. (b) Best found circuit for Walker-2d.

Fig. 13: Best evolved circuits for RL environments.

Fig. 14: Best found circuit for Mountaincar-Continuous.